

Male Nurses in Lebanon: Roles and Challenges in a Female-Dominated Field

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Abstract

Background: The nursing profession, historically feminized, remains marked by gender stereotypes that influence the perception of male nurses, particularly in societies where traditional roles are predominant, such as in Lebanon. This study aims to explore the perceptions, challenges, and contributions of male nurses in Lebanese hospitals.

Methodology: The study is based on a quantitative approach through a descriptive cross-sectional survey conducted among 120 male nurses working in public and private hospitals in Lebanon. Data collection was carried out via an online questionnaire distributed using the snowball sampling method. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software.

Results: The results show that most participants experienced obstacles related to gender stereotypes when choosing their profession, and the majority believe they face more difficulties than their female counterparts. The identified challenges include difficulty integrating into predominantly female teams, interactions with female patients, and lack of recognition or advancement opportunities. Furthermore, most participants consider that male nurses make a unique contribution to nursing care, particularly in managing physically demanding situations and enhancing the dynamics of mixed-gender teams.

Conclusion: The study highlights the need for better inclusion of male nurses in the field of nursing in Lebanon. It recommends awareness-raising actions to break stereotypes, training on diversity and inclusion, as well as the promotion of male role models within the profession.

Introduction

Nursing is widely recognized as a profession predominantly occupied by women [1, 2], rooted in traditional views of caregiving as a female responsibility. Although the number of male nurses is growing, they continue to face social and professional barriers that challenge their credibility in the field [3, 4, 5]. These include stereotypes questioning their emotional suitability [6], career motivations, and ability to provide compassionate care. In Lebanon, cultural norms and gender roles exacerbate these challenges, making it difficult for male nurses to integrate into teams, gain patients' trust, or receive recognition for their contributions [7, 8]. While existing research addresses gender bias in nursing globally, there is limited focus on the Lebanese context. This study aims to fill that gap by exploring the lived experiences of male nurses and analyzing how gender influences career choice, patient interactions, professional

integration, and their overall role in healthcare [9, 10, 11].

Methodology

Ethical Approval

This study was approved by the ethics committee of the Lebanese German University, ensuring compliance with ethical standards for research involving humans. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement, guaranteeing that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights. Participation was entirely voluntary, with no form of pressure exerted, and taking part in the study had no impact on participants' professional paths. The study posed no risk to their physical health or psychological well-being, and participants retained the right to withdraw at any time. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the research process.

More Information

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Study Design

This study was designed as a descriptive cross-sectional survey targeting male nurses working in public and private hospitals across Lebanon. Participants were recruited using a snowball sampling technique, which commenced with a small group of male nurses identified directly by the researchers or through professional contacts. These individuals were provided with an online questionnaire distributed via a secure WhatsApp link and were invited to share the link with other eligible colleagues. This recruitment strategy facilitated access to a dispersed nursing workforce across different hospitals and regions, ensured rapid dissemination of the survey, and enhanced sample diversity through professional and personal networks. A total of 120 nurses completed the questionnaire and were included in the final analysis.

Participants and Sampling

The research focused on male nurses employed in both public and private hospitals across Lebanon. Inclusion criteria required participants to understand French and provide informed consent. A snowball sampling method was employed, and the online survey was distributed via WhatsApp to ensure broad regional coverage.

Instrument

In this study, a questionnaire composed of seven sections was used to collect information on participation criteria, sociodemographic data, career motivations and choices, challenges encountered, perceptions and relationships with patients and staff, contributions and career perspectives, as well as participants' suggestions and recommendations. The form was designed so that informed consent and

inclusion criteria were mandatory statements to be selected before participants could proceed and answer the questions.

Data Analysis

Data collection occurred from December 1, 2024, to March 1, 2025, yielding 120 complete responses. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS, employing descriptive statistics and Chi-squared (χ^2) or Fisher's exact tests to examine associations. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The results highlight significant gender-related challenges faced by male nurses in Lebanon. A total of 55.8% reported encountering difficulties or reluctance in choosing nursing due to gender stereotypes. Additionally, 69.2% felt they face greater challenges than their female counterparts, particularly in areas such as integrating into female-led teams (25%), interacting with patients (23.3%), and advancing in their careers (15%). Despite these obstacles, 75% believed that male nurses offer distinct advantages, especially in tasks requiring physical strength (52.2%) and team management (12.2%). Significant correlations were found between the type of hospital and experiences of both discrimination and barriers to career choice ($p = 0.009$ and $p = 0.005$, respectively), as shown in Table 1. Table 2 indicates that years of experience ($p = 0.018$) and educational level ($p = 0.047$) were significantly associated with male nurses' interactions with female coworkers. Other independent variables such as age, department, and job position showed no significant correlations with most dependent variables.

Table 1: Study of the Relationships between Dependent Variables and Independent Variables

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	P Value	Presence of a significant relationship	Test
Did you experience any obstacles or hesitations (personal or external) when choosing this profession due to gender stereotypes?	Age	0.09	No	Fisher's exact test
	Years of experience	0.145	No	Chi-squared test
	Level of education	0.724	No	Fisher's exact test
	Type of hospital	0.009	Yes	Chi-squared test
	Job position	0.085	No	Fisher's exact test
	Department of work	0.657	No	Fisher's exact test
	Reason for choosing the profession	0.059	No	Chi-squared test
Do you think male nurses face more difficulties than their female colleagues do in the profession?	Age	0.858	No	Fisher's exact test
	Years of experience	0.099	No	Chi-squared test
	Level of education	0.747	No	Fisher's exact test
	Type of hospital	0.225	No	Chi-squared test
	Job position	0.576	No	Fisher's exact test
	Department of work	0.199	No	Fisher's exact test

	Reason for choosing the profession	0.868	No	Chi-squared test
Have you ever experienced discrimination or inappropriate behavior because of your gender?	Age	0.252	No	Fisher's exact test
	Years of experience	0.122	No	Chi-squared test
	Level of education	0.239	No	Fisher's exact test
	Type of hospital	0.005	Yes	Chi-squared test
	Job position	0.392	No	Fisher's exact test
	Department of work	0.991	No	Fisher's exact test
	Reason for choosing the profession	0.073	No	Chi-squared test
How do you perceive the relationship between male nurses and female patients? Are there differences in perception based on the gender of the professional?	Age	0.770	No	Fisher's exact test
	Years of experience	0.968	No	Chi-squared test
	Level of education	0.322	No	Fisher's exact test
	Type of hospital	0.047	Yes	Chi-squared test
	Job position	0.333	No	Fisher's exact test
	Department of work	0.386	No	Fisher's exact test
	Reason for choosing the profession	0.593	No	Chi-squared test

Table 2: Study of the Relationships between Dependent Variables and Independent Variables

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	P Value	Presence of a significant relationship	Test é
How would you describe your relationship with your female colleagues? Are there any particular challenges?	Age	0.242	No	Fisher's exact test
	Years of experience	0.018	Yes	Chi-squared test
	Level of education	0.047	Yes	Fisher's exact test
	Type of hospital	0.441	No	Chi-squared test
	Job position	0.302	No	Fisher's exact test
	Department of work	0.535	No	Fisher's exact test
	Reason for choosing the profession	0.141	No	Chi-squared test
Have you noticed a difference in perception between male patients and female patients towards male nurses?	Age	0.912	No	Fisher's exact test
	Years of experience	0.225	No	Chi-squared test
	Level of education	0.337	No	Fisher's exact test
	Type of hospital	0.486	No	Chi-squared test
	Job position	0.264	No	Fisher's exact test
	Department of work	0.665	No	Fisher's exact test
	Reason for choosing the profession	0.942	No	Chi-squared test
Do you think male nurses bring a unique or different contribution to nursing care?	Age	0.302	No	Chi-squared test
	Years of experience	0.053	No	Fisher's exact test
	Level of education	0.682	No	Fisher's exact test
	Type of hospital	0.082	No	Chi-squared test
	Job position	0.337	No	Fisher's exact test
	Department of work	0.140	No	Fisher's exact test
	Reason for choosing the profession	0.374	No	Chi-squared test
	Age	0.588	No	Chi-squared test
	Years of experience	0.395	No	Chi-squared test

How do you envision your future in this profession? Do you have any specific ambitions or career goals?	Level of education	0.353	No	Fisher's exact test
	Type of hospital	0.683	No	Chi-squared test
	Job position	0.665	No	Fisher's exact test
	Department of work	0.558	No	Fisher's exact test
	Reason for choosing the profession	0.548	No	Chi-squared test

Discussion

Although these results align with international studies on gender stereotypes in nursing [11], this research offers new insights by focusing on Lebanon, a context where these issues have been less explored. The persistence of cultural norms appears to exacerbate the challenges faced by male nurses such as social stigma, role misconceptions, and limited career advancement (Table 1). The type of hospital emerged as a key factor influencing experiences of discrimination and professional barriers, while education level and years of experience affected interprofessional dynamics (Table 2). These findings are consistent with those of Cleveland [12], who emphasized that local culture can amplify global gender stereotypes within healthcare professions. Conversely, some variables—such as age or role—did not show a significant association with perceived difficulties or role perceptions. Notably, beliefs about male nurses making unique contributions or facing greater challenges than their female counterparts were not significantly influenced by any independent factors (Tables 1 & 2), suggesting that these perceptions may be shaped more by cultural narratives than by professional status or experience. Addressing these challenges requires interventions at multiple levels, including public awareness campaigns, inclusive recruitment practices, promotion of male role models, and gender-sensitivity training in the workplace. Such measures could help normalize the presence of men in nursing and highlight the importance of gender balance within care teams—thereby enhancing both equity and quality of care.

Conclusion

This research highlights the shortage of male nurses in Lebanon and the challenges they encounter, emphasizing how gender stereotypes influence their career initiation, assimilation, and recognition. Despite these obstacles, male nurses believe they bring significant strengths to the profession. To create a more inclusive nursing workforce, stakeholders should raise awareness, revise institutional policies, and foster environments where diversity is valued as an asset rather than seen as an outlier. The essential question remains: How can we improve support and retention of male nurses in a culturally sensitive and professionally equitable manner?

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References

[1] American Institute for Boys and Men. Encouraging men into female-dominated jobs: A social work study [Internet]. 2024 Sep 23. Available from: <https://aibm.org/research/bridging-gender-gaps-social-work/>

[2] Historique - Institut de formation en soins infirmiers (Ifsi). Institut de Formation en Soins Infirmiers (Ifsi) [Internet]. 2021 Jun 23. Available from: <https://www.chu-poitiers.fr/specialites/formation-infirmier/historique/>

[3] Roy B, Holmes D, Chouinard V. Contribution à une éthique de la sollicitude: Masculinités et genre dans la profession infirmière. *Recherche en Soins Infirmiers*. 2011;107(4):38–48. doi:10.3917/rsi.107.0038

[4] Prosen M, Čekada T. Nursing students' views on men in nursing: a gender diversity challenge in the healthcare workforce. *BMC Nurs*. 2025 Jul 2;24:820. doi:10.1186/s12912-025-03521-y

[5] Smith BW, Rojo J, Everett B, Montayre J, Sierra J, Salamonson Y. Professional success of men in the nursing workforce: an integrative review. *J Nurs Manag*. 2021;29(8):2470–88. doi:10.1111/jonm.13445

[6] Gauci P, Luck L, O'Reilly K, Peters K. Workplace gender discrimination in the nursing workforce—An integrative review. *J Clin Nurs*. 2023;32(17–18). doi:10.1111/jocn.16684

[7] Au Liban, l'Ordre se bat pour garder ses infirmiers [Internet]. 2024. Available from: <https://www.infirmiers.com/profession-ide/au-liban-lordre-se-bat-pour-garder-ses-infirmiers>

[8] IzyFact. La profession infirmière est-elle essentiellement féminine ? (3/3) [Internet]. 2021 May 26. Available from: <https://www.izyfact.com/la-profession-infirmiere-est-elle-essentiellement-feminine-3-3/>

[9] Centre Kaizen. Diversité de genre en milieu de travail [Internet]. 2021. Available from: https://centrekaizenhaiti.com/uploads/documents/Diversit%C3%A9%20de%20genre%20en%20milieu%20de%20travail_Centre%20Kaizen_juin%202021.pdf

[10] Bouhon JP. Les défis du travail dans le secteur des soins de santé [Internet]. Fédération des maisons médicales; 2009. Available from: <https://www.maisonmedicale.org/les-defis-du-travail-dans-le/>

[11] Martínez-Morato S, Feijoo-Cid M, Galbany-Estragués P, Fernández-Cano MI, Arreciado Marañón A. Emotion management and stereotypes about emotions

among male nurses: a qualitative study. *BMC Nurs.* 2021;20(1):1–10. doi:10.1186/s12912-021-00641-z

[12] Cleveland Manchanda E, Chary A, Zaniel N, Nadeau L, Verstreken J, Shappell E, Macias-Konstantopoulos W, Dobiesz V. The role of gender in nurse-resident interactions: A mixed-methods study. *West J Emerg Med.* 2021;22(4):919–930. doi:10.5811/westjem.2021.3.49770

